

Supplemental Material for

Weather-Informed Imputation of Block-Missing Highway Speed Data

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Manuscript No. TEENG-9792

Journal of Transportation Engineering, Part A: Systems

This supplemental material provides additional speed-profile visualizations, per-round error summaries, correlation-preservation results, and storm-exclusion sensitivity tables supporting the revised manuscript. Figures and tables carry an “S” prefix (Fig. S1–S4, Table S1–S3) and are numbered independently of the main manuscript. All speed error metrics are reported in kilometers per hour (km/h; raw connected-vehicle speeds in mph converted by the factor 1.60934), matching the main manuscript.

Supplemental Figures

Figure S1. Scatter plot of all valid 10-minute average speed observations from 2022-09-27 to 2023-03-31. Three observation blocks are separated by extended block-missing gaps (Oct 29–Dec 10 and Dec 27–Feb 28), motivating the weather-informed imputation task. The Dec 23–25 winter storm peak is observed and is part of the storm-included three-round protocol (Round 3 test set). Naturally missing periods outside the held-out evaluation windows are used only for qualitative full-period imputation and are not included in any quantitative metric.

Figure S2. Per-round MAE across the three evaluation rounds, ordered by overall W-MAE rank. Every deep model except SAITS exhibits a sharp Round 3 degradation once Dec 23–25 (Buffalo Blizzard storm peak) is included in the test set; iTransformer in particular jumps from Round 1 MAE 2.85 to Round 3 MAE 5.65 km/h. SAITS remains the most consistent deep model across rounds.

Figure S3. Imputed-vs-ground-truth weather–speed correlation profiles for the top-six models across the three rounds. *Black line:* Pearson correlation between observed speed and each of the 20 weather and road-surface features (the subset visualized in the main-text ground-truth correlation figure) on the round’s test-period rows. *Coloured lines:* each model’s imputed-speed correlation on the same rows. The Corr-Pres distance (lower is better) is annotated per panel. Lines are visual guides to compare correlation-profile shapes across a fixed weather-feature order; the features are not a continuous physical axis.

Figure S4. Temporal speed structure. (a) Speed trend by time of day, averaged within each of five non-overlapping two-week windows; the Dec 12–25 winter window shows a distinctly lower and noisier diurnal profile, especially the late-day drop visible only in the winter trace, that motivates the cross-seasonal evaluation protocol. (b) Weekly speed pattern at 10-minute resolution; clear weekday morning- and evening-peak structures and a flatter weekend profile motivate the WdTodMean (weekday-time-of-day mean) temporal baseline.

Supplemental Tables

Table S1. Storm-excluded three-round evaluation protocol. Training and evaluation periods are non-overlapping and the Dec 23–25 Buffalo Blizzard window is excluded from every training and evaluation window; Round 3’s late-winter test window is Dec 19–22 only. Per-round N_{eval} are recomputed from the on-disk test files. This is the storm-excluded counterpart of the storm-included main-text protocol.

Round	Training periods	Evaluation periods	N_{eval}
1	Sep 28–Oct 13, Dec 12–22, Mar 16–30	Oct 14–28, Mar 1–15	4,296
2	Sep 28–Oct 13, Dec 19–22, Mar 16–30	Oct 14–28, Dec 12–18, Mar 1–15	5,304
3	Sep 28–Oct 13, Dec 12–18, Mar 16–30	Oct 14–28, Dec 19–22, Mar 1–15	4,872

Note: Total evaluation timesteps $4,296 + 5,304 + 4,872 = 14,472$. N_{eval} excludes 24 genuinely missing speed points on 2022-10-28 shared across all three rounds’ test sets.

Table S2. Final multi-seed ranking on the storm-excluded three-round protocol (true km/h, lower is better). W-MAE is the cell-count weighted mean absolute error with storm-excluded weights 4,296/5,304/4,872 (total 14,472). Mean \pm std across seeds; deterministic models show no \pm std. Compare with the storm-included headline table in the main manuscript: the best storm-excluded W-MAE is ≈ 2.47 km/h (CSDI \approx SAITS) versus the storm-included best of 3.15 km/h (SAITS).

Model	Type	R1	R2	R3	W-MAE	W-RMSE
CSDI	deep	2.28 ± 0.17	2.63 ± 0.04	2.46 ± 0.17	2.47 ± 0.03	4.44 ± 0.02
SAITS	deep	2.24 ± 0.05	2.90 ± 0.08	2.21 ± 0.05	2.47 ± 0.02	4.23 ± 0.12
HGBT	classical	2.37	2.69	2.45	2.51	4.66
GBDT	classical	2.55 ± 0.01	2.63 ± 0.00	2.48 ± 0.00	2.55 ± 0.00	4.67 ± 0.01
RandomForest	classical	2.68 ± 0.01	2.74 ± 0.01	2.62 ± 0.02	2.68 ± 0.01	4.84 ± 0.02
FGTI	deep	2.41 ± 0.02	3.29 ± 0.06	2.44 ± 0.06	2.74 ± 0.01	4.75 ± 0.12
TimesNet	deep	2.53 ± 0.04	3.31 ± 0.11	2.60 ± 0.08	2.84 ± 0.06	4.69 ± 0.14
BRITS	deep	2.75 ± 0.19	3.11 ± 0.04	2.66 ± 0.22	2.85 ± 0.14	4.71 ± 0.16
iTransformer	deep	2.67 ± 0.02	3.20 ± 0.00	2.67 ± 0.05	2.86 ± 0.03	4.95 ± 0.02
Ridge	classical	2.96 ± 0.00	2.99	2.87 ± 0.00	2.94 ± 0.00	4.74
LinearRegression	classical	3.02 ± 0.00	3.03 ± 0.00	2.92	2.99 ± 0.00	4.81
GRIN	deep	2.95 ± 0.14	3.57 ± 0.00	2.95 ± 0.03	3.17 ± 0.05	5.46 ± 0.04
PatchTST	deep	3.06 ± 0.19	3.62 ± 0.17	3.10 ± 0.03	3.28 ± 0.09	5.39 ± 0.09
SSSD	deep	3.36 ± 0.02	3.73 ± 0.01	3.36 ± 0.10	3.50 ± 0.03	5.66 ± 0.06
TodMean	temporal	2.80	3.18	2.72	2.91	5.09
TrMean	temporal	3.25	3.60	3.18	3.35	5.44
WdTodMean	temporal	2.77	2.93	2.77	2.83	4.95

Table S3. Single-season sensitivity MAE (km/h, lower is better). Each model was trained on one season’s training window only and evaluated on that season’s held-out test window: Autumn (train 2022-09-28 to 10-13, test 10-14 to 10-28; $N = 2,136$), Winter (train 2022-12-12 to 12-18, test 12-19 to 12-25, including the Dec 23–25 storm peak; $N = 1,008$), and Spring (train 2023-03-16 to 03-30, test 03-01 to 03-15; $N = 2,160$). Hyperparameters are taken verbatim from the main benchmark (a sensitivity check, not a re-tuning); seed 42 for all models, with iTransformer also run at seeds 1337 and 2024 (negligible variation, $\sigma_{\text{MAE}_{\text{Winter}}} = 0.13$ km/h). iTransformer is the three-seed mean; all other rows are single-seed. Winter-only training degrades by roughly 5–10 \times relative to Autumn- or Spring-only and is roughly 2–4 \times worse than the same models’ storm-included Round 3 MAE in the main multi-seed benchmark, confirming the benefit of the cross-season three-round training schema.

Model	Family	Autumn-only	Winter-only	Spring-only
SAITS	Attention (imputation)	2.00	11.27	2.27
HGBT	Classical	1.85	12.36	2.48
RandomForest	Classical	1.75	13.86	2.48
LinearRegression	Classical	2.69	11.70	2.43
TimesNet	Attention (forecasting)	2.20	12.89	2.66
iTransformer	Attention (forecasting)	3.11	19.28	3.41
BRITS	Recurrent	2.08	12.68	2.75
GRIN	Graph	2.72	18.56	3.07
CSDI	Diffusion	2.16	18.11	2.53
SSSD	Diffusion	2.77	19.07	3.20